

Bedrock Geological Map Predictions for Phanerozoic Fossil Occurrences

Supplementary figures

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Figure S1

Figure S1: An illustrative figure demonstrating the spatiotemporal intersection between the PBDB collections and the Macrostrat map data.

Figure S2

Figure S2: We calculated the residuals of each polygon and map units (with at least 1 fossil occurrence) after fitting the simple linear regression model between the fossil occurrence and map area. The residual-area plots at the granular polygon (A) and map unit (B) levels show heteroscedasticity but uncorrelated residuals with no systematic positive-negative trends. We performed an area-occurrence trajectory modeling for the North American and European dataset with the following steps: 1) We graded the polygons by size into arbitrary categorical ranges; 2) In each category, we take one random polygon and record its area and number of fossil occurrences; 3) We randomly take another polygon in the same category and add its area and occurrences to the existing polygon to get the sum of the area and fossil occurrences between these 2 polygons; 4) We repeat this process in the same category. If the sum of the polygon areas never reaches the upper limit of the category, then a total of 10 polygons will be drawn from this category one by one, and the area-occurrence trajectory will be recorded. If the total area reaches the upper limit of the category before reaching 10 polygons, then the process stops in this category and moves to the next category of bigger polygons; 5) At the next category, one random polygon is drawn and its area and number of fossil occurrences are recorded (in each category the trajectory starts with a single polygon, which means the previous category's records will be cleared once the process starts in a new category). We ran the simulation for 1,000 times at granular polygon (C) and map units (D) levels. Area and occurrences show a generally linear relationship.

Figure S3

Figure S3: The distributions of polygon areas in each region.